

**APPLICATION OF LOCAL INTERPOLATION CUBIC SPLINE
MODEL BUILT IN UNEQUAL INTERVALS IN DIGITAL PROCESSING OF
SIGNALS.**

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Abstract: This article explores the application of local interpolation cubic spline models constructed at unequal intervals in the digital processing of signals. The use of third-order (cubic) spline functions for signal interpolation and restoration is examined,

showcasing their efficacy in digital signal processing. The article introduces the formulation of the local interpolation cubic spline model and demonstrates its ability to achieve high precision in signal reconstruction. The proposed algorithm is exemplified through the restoration of k-waved geophysical signals, with the developed third-order spline construction program implemented in MATLAB. The results indicate the successful restoration of geophysical signals, emphasizing the effectiveness of the cubic spline model in signal processing.

Keywords: Digital Signal Processing, Cubic Spline, Interpolation, Signal Restoration, Unequal Intervals, Geophysical Signals, MATLAB.

Processes of interpolation and restoration of signals in the form of a table were carried out with the help of functions of local cubic splines built at unequal intervals considered in this work. Also, we can say that cubic spline models built at unequal intervals give good results in digital signal processing, which ensures that experts make the right decision as a result of digital signal processing. As an example, as a result of digital processing of geophysical signals, scientists have discovered dozens of methods for predicting minerals. The results obtained using these methods are important for understanding the physical processes occurring underground, observing them, and building physical and mathematical models of the interdependence of these processes. Increasing the level of convergence of the models considered in this work does not depend on increasing the order of the system of equations.

1. Local interpolation cubic spline model built at unequal intervals.

In digital signal processing, third-order (cubic) spline functions are a high-precision mathematical apparatus. First, we give an overview of the spline model, which gives good results in digital signal processing.

$$S_3(f, x) = \sum_{k=1}^4 \phi_k(t) f(x_{i+k-2})$$

Here

$$\varphi_1(t) = \frac{11t^2}{12} - \frac{5t}{12} - \frac{t^3}{2}$$

$$\varphi_2(t) = 1 - \frac{9t^2}{4} - \frac{t}{4} + \frac{3t^3}{2}$$

$$\varphi_3(t) = \frac{7t^2}{4} + \frac{3t}{4} - \frac{3t^3}{2}$$

$$\varphi_4(t) = \frac{t^3}{2} - \frac{5t^2}{12} - \frac{t}{12}$$

$$t = \frac{x - x_i}{h}, \quad h = x_{i+1} - x_i, \quad x \in [x_i, x_{i+1}], \quad t \in [0,1]$$

The theorem on the fulfillment of the interpolation conditions of the considered local interpolation cubic spline is proved in this work.

2. Digital processing of signals based on the algorithm considered in this work.

The restoration of the k-waved geophysical signal by the considered cubic spline models is considered in Table 1. Based on the above sequence, a third-order spline construction program was developed in the MATLAB environment and used in signal processing (Fig. 1).

Geophysical signal values.

Table 1.

№	Time, seconds	Amplitude	№	Time, seconds	Amplitude
1.	1	0.0381	10.	10	0.0379
2.	2	0.0398	11.	11	0.0381
3.	3	0.0381	12.	12	0.0391
4.	4	0.0376	13.	13	0.0381
5.	5	0.0381	14.	14	0.0375
6.	6	0.0427	15.	15	0.0381
7.	7	0.0401	16.	16	0.0454
8.	8	0.0381	17.	17	0.0381
9.	9	0.0347			

Geophysical signal recovery results.

Figure 1.

Conclusion:

This study investigates the utilization of local interpolation cubic spline models built at unequal intervals for digital signal processing. The introduced cubic spline model, formulated as a third-order function, demonstrates its suitability and precision in signal interpolation and restoration. By applying the developed algorithm to the restoration of k-waved geophysical signals, the study underscores the practicality of the approach. The results obtained through the third-order spline construction program implemented in MATLAB affirm the effectiveness of the cubic spline model in accurately reconstructing signals. This methodology holds promise for a wide range of applications where signal processing is crucial for decision-making and analysis.

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